

#15

Evaluation & Impact Assessment IMPACT STORIES

<p>MAA Scenario</p> <p>ENGAGING & INCENTIVISING INTERROGATING CREATING ADDRESSING APPLYING</p>	
<p>When to Implement</p>	<p>After an actor/stakeholder has engaged with a project or part of a project to assess the impact of the project where that actor is concerned.</p>
<p>Group Size</p>	<p>One to one</p>
<p>Level of Technical Difficulty</p>	<p>No technical expertise required.</p>
<p>Time Needed</p>	<p>30 minutes-2 hours (depending on length of story).</p>
<p>Resources Required</p>	<p>Optional transcription of the impact story.</p>
<p>Clustering with Other Tools</p>	<p>Tools # 5, 6, 11, 14.</p>

PURPOSE, BACKGROUND & LOGIC

Image source: Teagasc

Purpose

This tool is used to:

- Understand the experiences of an actor/stakeholder with a project/initiative, identifying impacts of the project/initiative and their subjective evaluations of the project/initiative.
- Understand the actor's/stakeholder's experiences, pinpointing events where the project/initiative had impact/s and eliciting a detailed description of these.
- Understand the experiences and learnings that give rise to impact.
- Assess the extent to which the actor's/stakeholder's experiences match with what the project/initiative envisaged and intended, pinpointing particular events and experiences.

Background and Logic

Tools such as Tool #11 (causes and effects) and Tools #5 and #6 (needs and motivations registers) generate hypotheses and collect information about intended impacts of a project/initiative and what actors/stakeholders want from a project/initiative. These are very important planning tools in making reflexive, evidence-based decisions that are attuned to different actors' & stakeholders' needs & motivations in real-life circumstances. However, as the project/initiative progresses and/or matures to completion what were participants' experiences in practice?

This tool is similar to Tool#14, but takes a more in-depth approach. Instead of presenting the story of impact in a concise storyboard format, this tool elicits a detailed narrative about an actor's/stakeholder's experiences. This tool is inspired by the 'performance story' approach ([Vanclay, 2012](#)). The method of eliciting the narrative/story draws from [Wengraf \(2008\)](#).

Materials:

- Audio recording device for transcription of the narrative to text format.
- Appropriate procedures for compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation ([GDPR](#)).

METHOD/HOW-TO GUIDE

Step 1: Preparation

Explain the purpose, logic and background of the tool.

Step 2: Facilitator preparation¹

- The facilitator acts in an interviewer role. An open ended approach is taken, inviting the actor/stakeholder to tell their story. No question list of pre-prepared questions is used. The role of the facilitator is to listen and, if necessary, limit questions only to asking more detail about what the actor/stakeholder has told them.
- It may be the case that a key planned impact does not arise in the story and if so, this is likely to indicate that the impact did not occur or lacked significance. In such a way, what is absent from the story can be as important as what is in the story.
- The facilitator should prepare him/herself, where relevant, with a list of the key events/impacts planned by the project/initiative for the actor/stakeholder so that s/he can be attentive to how these are (or are not) portrayed in the story.
- Considering that the story is about interactive innovation, the facilitator should also be attentive to the various multi-actor scenarios – what were the actor's/stakeholder's experiences of these important scenarios in interactive innovation?

- The most important prompt questions to elicit a story type narrative for populating the storyboard are:
 - » Can you tell me the story of your experiences of (project/initiative), all the experiences and events that are important to you personally. Start from the beginning.
 - » The facilitator (who is acting in a role similar to that of an interviewer) can ask for more detail on the story, such as:
 - Can you tell me more about how all that happened?
 - Do you remember anything more about that particular moment/time?

Step 3: Use of the Story/Narrative to assess/evaluate the project/initiative

- The story portrays participant/s experiences of the project/initiative, telling the story of all impacts as experienced by the participant/s. It provides evidence of the more immeasurable, experiential and unintended as well as intended impact/s of the project/initiative.
- Processes of interactive innovation, such as the key scenarios of multi-actor work, are qualitatively described.
- Whether the intended impacts of the project were experienced by the participant/s (and how significant they were) can be assessed.
- Stories portraying different actors' experiences of the project/initiative can be used to assess varying impacts of the project/initiative among actor types.

Multi-Actor toolbox – online, interactive version (with links to practical tools) available [here](#).

¹ This approach is inspired by the Biographic Narrative Interpretive Method (BNIM) [Wengraf \(2008\)](#)

